

1 Enhanced cleaning of sink drains alters the bacterial community in plumbing components but not
2 on countertop surfaces

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17

18 **Abstract**

19 Hospital sink drainage systems serve as reservoirs for healthcare-associated pathogens, yet the
20 ecological mechanisms of effective antimicrobial control remain poorly understood. We conducted
21 a 35-week longitudinal study comparing sink microbiomes in 30 hospital rooms treated with
22 hydrogen peroxide-based, acid-mixture versus untreated controls. Using 16S rRNA sequencing of
23 1,957 samples from tail pieces, P-traps, and countertops, we characterized treatment effects on
24 community structure and pathogen abundance. Treatment reduced genus richness by 50% in
25 plumbing components but had no effect on the countertop. Critically, genera that contain
26 ESKAPEE pathogens (*Klebsiella*, *Acinetobacter*, and *Enterobacter*) were significantly enriched in
27 untreated sinks, while treated communities were dominated by soil- and water-associated bacteria,
28 with *Bradyrhizobium* showing the strongest effect. Treatment created a "controlled instability"
29 signature with reduced temporal autocorrelation and directional drift, disrupting biofilm
30 succession without chaotic fluctuations. Treatment effects were detectable from week 1 and
31 sustained throughout the study. Differential abundance analysis revealed 85% of treatment-
32 enriched genera were environmental bacteria, indicating ecological replacement rather than
33 sterilization. Our findings demonstrate that effective antimicrobial treatment establishes
34 alternative community states that resist pathogen colonization while maintaining environmental
35 responsiveness, challenging traditional sterilization-based approaches to healthcare environment
36 management.

37

38 **Importance**

39 Hospital-acquired infections represent a major public health burden affecting millions annually.
40 This study reveals that effective pathogen control operates through ecological replacement rather
41 than sterilization. A hydrogen peroxide-based treatment established stable microbial communities
42 dominated by environmental bacteria that consistently resist colonization by pathogen-containing
43 groups, like *Klebsiella* and *Enterobacter*. Treatment effects were immediate and sustained over 35
44 weeks, indicating robust protection. Unlike traditional approaches that aim to eliminate all
45 microbes, this ecological strategy maintains community responsiveness while preventing pathogen
46 establishment. These findings demonstrate that carefully managed bacterial communities provide

47 sustainable pathogen control, offering a paradigm shift for healthcare environment management
48 from broad suppression to targeted ecological intervention.

49

50 **Introduction**

51 Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) pose a significant health risk, with 1 in 31 patients
52 infected with an HAI daily, resulting in 72,000 deaths per year in the USA alone¹. Many of these
53 HAIs are caused by exposure to bacteria that are classified as ESKAPEE pathogens (*Enterococcus*
54 *faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas*
55 *aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter* spp., and *Escherichia coli*)²; a group that is characterized by their ability
56 to form biofilms.³ These biofilms increase bacterial survival, and they can serve as a reservoir for
57 plasmids carrying antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes⁴, promoting AMR gene transfer⁵.
58 Additionally, there is increased selection for biofilm-forming bacteria in more extreme
59 environments, contributing to a greater diversity and prevalence of ESKAPEE-associated AMR
60 genes in clinical settings when compared to their environmental counterparts^{6,7}. This is of
61 particular concern on surfaces that are difficult to access or clean with standard hospital sanitation
62 methods, including plumbing components.

63 Hospital sinks are known hotspots for pathogen accumulation and dispersal in patient
64 rooms^{8,9}, with studies showing that ICU rooms with sinks are associated with higher rates of HAIs
65 compared to sink-free units¹⁰. The P-trap, in particular, functions as a primary pathogen reservoir.
66 It retains standing water, providing a nutrient-rich, moist environment that supports biofilm
67 establishment and microbial persistence^{11,12}. Quantitative analyses have demonstrated that P-trap
68 biofilms harbor significantly elevated concentrations of opportunistic pathogens, including *P.*
69 *aeruginosa* and carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae, with bacterial densities exceeding
70 10^8 colony-forming units per surface area^{12,13}. Further, P-trap biofilms exhibit active upward
71 growth dynamics that enable pathogen translocation from the P-trap to more accessible drain
72 components, such as the tail piece¹¹. Although removal of sinks from patient rooms would likely
73 reduce infection rates¹⁰, this would require costly redesign and renovation of entire hospital units.
74 Alternative methods might include heating the tail piece¹⁴, using materials with antimicrobial
75 properties (e.g., copper)¹⁵, application of ozone¹⁶, and the use of steam or boiling water¹⁷.

76 However, these approaches can be costly or difficult to deploy at hospital-wide scales,
77 necessitating tractable disinfection practices that target these locations.

78 New approaches use foaming agents combined with disinfectants, such as hydrogen
79 peroxide and peroxyacetic acid, to prolong contact time with the treated surface. This has been
80 shown to effectively reduce colonization by gram-negative bacteria¹⁸, opportunistic premise
81 plumbing pathogens (OPPPs)¹⁹, and epidemiologically important pathogens (EIPs)²⁰. Here, we
82 applied an antimicrobial foaming agent to hospital sinks in patient rooms at Duke University
83 Hospital within a newly renovated intermediate care unit (IMCU); a unit that houses patients that
84 require a care-level between general patient care and the ICU. Prior to cleaner application and
85 sample collection, plumbing components were installed and rooms had not yet been occupied by
86 patients. For half of the sinks, a foaming hydrogen peroxide/peracetic acid solution was applied to
87 the sink tail piece three times per week (Monday, Wednesday, Friday), and samples were collected
88 one day per week (Tuesday) from three locations, including the tail piece, P-trap, and countertop.
89 We then sequenced the full-length 16S rRNA gene to assess differences in bacterial community
90 dynamics at different temporal and spatial scales. Additionally, we examined how observed
91 changes in community structure influenced the relative abundance of bacteria of concern and
92 identified taxa that are negatively correlated with ESKAPEE bacteria to determine potential targets
93 for bioremediation efforts to reduce exposure and infection risk.

94

95 **Methods**

96 *Study Design*

97 The study was conducted in a newly renovated IMCU at Duke University Hospital; a 1048-bed
98 tertiary care hospital located in Durham, North Carolina, USA, as previously described²⁰. Sink-
99 associated samples were collected from the P-trap, tail piece, and countertop of 30 sinks over a 35-
100 week period, starting in July of 2024. Samples were collected once per week (Tuesday), and
101 collection began one week prior to patient occupation. Of the 30 rooms, half were randomly
102 selected to receive an enhanced cleaning intervention three times a week (Monday, Wednesday,
103 Friday). The enhanced cleaning product, Virasept (Ecolab, # 6002314), is a peroxide-based, acid-
104 mixture liquid with three key active ingredients: hydrogen peroxide (3.13%), peroxyacetic acid
105 (0.05%), and octanoic acid (0.099%). Virasept is sold as a liquid product, but when pumped

106 through an applicator, forms a foam that remains within the tail piece for at least 5 minutes.
107 Throughout the study duration, all rooms were cleaned per the standard hospital cleaning
108 procedure, which includes daily surface disinfection with non-bleach solutions.

109

110 *Sample collection and processing*

111 Tail piece samples were collected using a Copen ESwab (BD, # 220245) that was inserted through
112 the sink drain and rubbed against the internal surface of the tail piece, while applying pressure and
113 rotating. The swab was transferred into the storage medium to elute the sample and was centrifuged
114 at 10,000 x g for 1 minute to pellet the cells. The resulting cell pellet was transferred to a lysis
115 tube. P-trap samples were collected using a syringe and tubing. The syringe was pumped several
116 times to resuspend settled particles and 15 mL of liquid was retained. This liquid was vacuum
117 filtered through a 0.22-micron filter (Omicron Scientific, # 170047) on a fritted glass support base.
118 The filter was shredded with flame sterilized scissors and tweezers, then inserted into a PowerSoil
119 Pro (Qiagen, # 47126) lysis tube. Lastly, countertop samples were collected using a cellulose
120 sponge pre-moistened in phosphate buffered saline with 1% Tween 20. Following collection, the
121 sponge was processed using the stomacher technique in accordance with the Centers for Disease
122 Control and Prevention protocol²¹. After collection, sponges were placed in stomacher bags with
123 45 mL of phosphate-buffered saline with 1% Tween 20 and then homogenized for 60 seconds at
124 260 rpm. Homogenates were then centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 10 minutes. The supernatant was
125 removed, and the pellet was collected with a sterile cotton swab (Puritan, # 806-WC). The tip of
126 the cotton swab was then cut off into a PowerSoil Pro lysis tube. All samples were stored at -20°C
127 until DNA extraction.

128

129 *DNA extraction and sequencing*

130 DNA was extracted following the manufacturer's instructions with the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro kit
131 (QIAGEN) and quantified using a Qubit dsDNA BR Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher, # Q32853).
132 Samples with DNA concentrations > 1 ng/μl were normalized to 1 ng/μl; samples below this
133 threshold were not normalized. A 2 μl aliquot of each sample was then subjected to PCR
134 amplification of the full-length 16S rRNA gene following the PacBio Kinnex 16S kit protocol

135 (PacBio), using Phusion Plus PCR Master Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific, # F631L) and 27F -
136 1492R universal primer pair (5'-AGRGGTTYGATYMTGGCTCAG-3' and 5'-
137 RGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3', respectively). Primers with unique barcodes and Kinnex
138 adaptor sequences were used at a final concentration of 0.3 μ M. Reaction mixes were denatured
139 for 30 seconds at 98°C prior to 30 cycles of denaturation at 98°C for 10 seconds, annealing at 57°C
140 for 20 seconds, and extension at 72°C for 75 seconds. After the last cycle, a final extension at 72°C
141 for 5 minutes was performed. Completed PCR reactions were visualized on an E-Gel (Invitrogen)
142 to ensure that amplicon size was correct (~1500bp), and that each sample amplified appropriately.
143 Amplicon libraries were subsequently pooled at different volumes, based on gel band intensity (1,
144 2.5, 5, 10, or 20 μ l per reaction). The pooled libraries were cleaned and concentrated using 1.1X
145 volume of SMRTbell® cleanup beads (PacBio) and eluted in 50 μ l of low TE elution buffer
146 (PacBio). Cleaned libraries were stored at -20°C prior to Kinnex PCR for concatenation and
147 circularization. Kinnex PCR was performed as outlined in the PacBio Kinnex 16S kit's published
148 protocol with no modifications (PacBio). Size selected and cleaned libraries were loaded onto a
149 PacBio SMRT® Cell and sequenced on the Revo system (PacBio) at the Duke Sequencing and
150 Genomic Technologies (SGT) Shared Resource facility.

151

152 *Data analysis*

153 Circular consensus sequencing (CCS) data were quality filtered (Q20), de-concatenated,
154 demultiplexed, and converted from .bam to .fastq format in the SMRT Link software system
155 (PacBio). Barcode and adapter sequences were removed using the q2-demux plugin²².
156 Demultiplexed full-length 16S rRNA amplicon sequences were analyzed with DADA2²² and
157 QIIME2²³ following the developers' instructions. Denoising, dereplication, ASV inference, and
158 chimera removal were performed with the DADA2 long-read pipeline. Taxonomy was assigned
159 with QIIME2 feature classifier using the GTDB database (release 220)²⁴. Abundance values were
160 normalized by multiplying the relative abundance by the average sequencing depth, as previously
161 described²⁵. Statistical analyses were performed in R (v. 4.3.1)²⁶.

162 Community turnover was quantified as the week-to-week Bray-Curtis dissimilarity
163 between consecutive sampling timepoints within each room and sampling location. For each room,
164 all adjacent timepoint pairs were identified by sorting samples by week, and the mean pairwise

165 dissimilarity was calculated as a per-room turnover score. Differences in turnover between treated
166 and untreated sinks were tested by Wilcoxon rank-sum test within each sampling location. To
167 assess when treatment effects emerged over the study period, a per-week PERMANOVA was
168 performed for each week that had sufficient paired samples, using treatment as the predictor
169 variable within each sampling location.

170 Community instability was characterized using three complementary approaches, all based
171 on Aitchison distance. First, per-room volatility was quantified as the mean step distance between
172 consecutive weekly samples. Second, temporal autocorrelation was assessed by computing the lag-
173 1 Pearson autocorrelation of each room's distance-from-centroid time series, where the centroid
174 was defined as the mean CLR vector across all timepoints for that room; rooms with fewer than
175 four timepoints were excluded. A positive lag-1 autocorrelation (ACF) indicates that the
176 community exhibits temporal dependence over time, while a value near zero indicates
177 unpredictable week-to-week dynamics. Third, per-room PERMANOVA R^2 was calculated by
178 fitting week as the sole predictor of Aitchison distances within each room, where high R^2 indicates
179 directional community drift over time and low R^2 indicates a stable or randomly fluctuating
180 community. Differences in volatility, ACF, and PERMANOVA R^2 between treatment groups were
181 tested by Wilcoxon rank-sum tests for each sampling location.

182 Alpha diversity was assessed using the Chao1 richness estimator and Shannon diversity
183 index. Differences in alpha diversity between treated and untreated sinks were tested separately
184 for each sampling location (tail piece, P-trap, countertop) using Wilcoxon rank-sum tests with
185 Benjamini-Hochberg correction for multiple comparisons. Beta-diversity was calculated using
186 Aitchison distance, calculated using a centered log-ratio (CLR) transformation with a half-
187 minimum pseudocount and Euclidean distance²⁷. Differences in bacterial community profiles
188 between treatment groups were tested using PERMANOVA with the 'adonis2' function with 999
189 permutations and strata set to room to account for the paired room-level treatment design²⁸. Beta-
190 dispersion (homogeneity of within-group variance) was assessed using the 'betadisper' function
191 in vegan²⁸, and variance partitioning was performed using the 'varpart' function on Hellinger-
192 transformed community matrices, to quantify the independent contributions of treatment, sample
193 type, week, and room to community composition²⁹.

194 Differential abundance of individual taxa between treated and untreated sinks was assessed
195 using ALDEx2³⁰ with Welch's t-test and Wilcoxon rank-sum test, using 128 Monte Carlo Dirichlet
196 instances to propagate compositional uncertainty. Taxa present in fewer than 5% of samples within
197 an individual sampling location were excluded. Effect sizes are reported as the difference between
198 the group median log-ratio abundances, and significance was assessed using Benjamini-Hochberg-
199 corrected p-values from both the parametric and non-parametric tests. A negative effect size is
200 enrichment in the treated samples, whereas a positive effect is enrichment in the control samples.

201 To characterize the ecological niches frequently occupied by the differentially abundant
202 taxa, genera identified to be significant were classified into functional groups: oligotrophic
203 environmental bacteria (soil rhizobia and alphaproteobacterial water-associated taxa), disinfectant-
204 tolerant bacteria, transient human commensals (skin- and oral-associated taxa), mature biofilm
205 specialists (*Sphingomonadales* and co-occurring pipe biofilm community members), and clinically
206 relevant groups (ESKAPEE pathogens). Indicator species analysis was performed using the
207 'multipatt' function in the indicpecies package³¹ with 999 permutations to identify genera
208 significantly associated with treated or untreated sinks within each sampling location. Co-
209 occurrence networks were constructed for P-trap samples using Spearman correlations between
210 genera recovered from at least 20% of samples, retaining edges with $|r| > 0.3$ and Benjamini-
211 Hochberg-corrected $p < 0.05$, and network properties were compared, to assess whether treatment
212 disrupts co-occurrence structure.

213

214 **Results**

215 *Community Volatility and Instability Analysis*

216 Overall, bacterial community volatility did not differ significantly between the treated and
217 untreated sinks for all three locations (Fig. 1A, Aitchison distance: tail piece $P = 0.362$, P-trap $P =$
218 0.709 , countertop $P = 0.340$). However, week-to-week compositional change revealed complex
219 temporal dynamics (Fig. 1B). There were statistically significant differences between treatment
220 groups, with 19 of 34 weeks in tail piece samples, 14 of 34 weeks showing variation in P-trap
221 samples, and only 1 of 34 weeks in countertop samples (Table S1; Wilcoxon rank-sum tests, $P <$
222 0.05). The weeks that exhibited community volatility occurred sporadically throughout the study
223 period with no consistent patterns or directionality. Temporal clustering of significant weeks (e.g.,

224 weeks 21-26) could suggest small, but consistent, treatment-specific responses to facility-wide
225 environmental conditions, evidenced by overlapping confidence intervals that nonetheless yielded
226 statistically significant differences due to consistent separation of underlying room-level
227 distributions (Fig. 1A, Table S1).

228 Complementary analysis of temporal stability patterns revealed that treated bacterial
229 communities had altered ecological dynamics compared to untreated communities. Lag-1 temporal
230 autocorrelation analysis showed that tail piece communities displayed significantly lower week-
231 to-week predictability than those from untreated samples ($W = 62$, $P = 0.038$), with treated
232 communities exhibiting near-zero autocorrelation (-0.06) compared to positive autocorrelation in
233 untreated communities (0.16) (Fig. 2A). No significant differences were found in the P-traps ($P =$
234 0.590) or on countertops ($P = 0.967$), with the countertops having a high ACF in both groups
235 (~ 0.35). Additionally, per-room PERMANOVA analysis showed that temporal drift patterns
236 differed between treatments, with the week of study explaining significantly less compositional
237 variance in treated communities (tail piece: 6-8% variance, significant in 7-20% of rooms)
238 compared to untreated sinks (11% variance, significant in 80-87% of rooms) (Fig. 2B, $P < 0.0001$).
239 Similarly, in P-traps, treatment explained 5-7% variance based on week of sample collection
240 (significant in 15-25% of rooms), compared to 10-12% variance in untreated sinks (significant in
241 75-85% of rooms) ($P = 0.011$). There was no reduction in temporal drift among treated
242 communities for countertop samples (Fig. 2B, $P = 0.481$).

243 Joint analysis of autocorrelation and directional drift patterns showed distinct temporal
244 stability dynamics. Treated communities, which clustered predominantly in the lower-left quadrant
245 of the ACF vs R^2 space (Fig. 2C), were characterized by low temporal predictability and minimal
246 directional drift. This controlled instability signature was most pronounced in plumbing
247 components, with minimal overlap of untreated communities in tail piece and P-trap samples, but
248 not among countertops. Group centroids (diamond markers) confirmed that treated plumbing
249 communities have a distinct signature that is characterized by disrupted week-to-week
250 predictability (low ACF) combined with reduced long-term directional change (low R^2). These
251 results were reflected in species diversity and taxonomic compositional assessments.

252

253 *Community Richness and Diversity*

254 Treated tail pieces and P-traps had significantly less richness (Chao1: $P < 0.001$), with nearly half
255 the average number of predicted genera (Fig. 3A, treated: tail piece = 13.5, P-trap = 25.1; untreated:
256 tail piece = 25.4, P-trap = 41.3). Consistent with our other findings, there was no observable effect
257 on richness among countertop samples ($P = 0.211$). When evenness was considered, treated P-traps
258 had significantly lower diversity (Shannon: $P = 0.0026$), but there were no differences in tail pieces
259 or on countertops (Fig. 3A, Shannon: $P = 0.573$ and $P = 0.330$, respectively).

260 Additionally, there were differences in the overall community structure between treated
261 and untreated samples from tail pieces and P-traps ($P = 0.001$ for both), with no observable
262 differences at the countertop locations ($P = 0.180$) (Fig. 3B), despite frequent identification of the
263 most abundant taxa across all three surfaces. These included common sink-associated bacteria
264 (e.g., *Pseudomonas*, *Spingomonas*, *Cupriavidus*), body associates (e.g., *Staphylococcus*,
265 *Veillonella*), and environmentally-sourced groups (e.g., *Bradyrhizobium*, *Methylobacterium*,
266 *Novosphingobium*) (Fig. 4). Therefore, to further assess which taxa were driving the observed
267 differences in community membership, a differential abundance analysis was performed.

268

269 *Differentially Abundant Taxa*

270 Based on treatment, there were 22 significant genera in tail pieces and 41 significant genera in P-
271 traps, while no genera were significantly differentially abundant among countertops (Fig. 5, Table
272 1). Additionally, there was a strong positive correlation between tail piece and P-trap responses (r
273 = 0.611, $P < 0.001$) that demonstrated consistent, rather than stochastic, changes in the community-
274 level response.

275 Treated-enriched genera were predominantly soil- and water-associated bacteria (~85%),
276 including nitrogen-fixing rhizosphere bacteria (*Bradyrhizobium*, *Mesorhizobium*), spore-forming
277 soil bacteria (*Bacillus*, *Sporosarcina*, *Paenibacillus*), environmental actinobacteria
278 (*Rhodococcus*), and freshwater-associated taxa (*Pelomonas*). *Bradyrhizobium* had the strongest
279 enrichment in treated samples across both locations (tail piece: effect = -0.801, $P < 0.0001$; P-trap:
280 effect = -0.625, $P < 0.0001$), along with other environmental taxa, such as *Afipia* (a plant-associated
281 Alphaproteobacteria, effect = -0.459 to -0.151) and *Mycobacterium* (Table 1).

282 Conversely, untreated samples were significantly enriched for genera that contain
283 opportunistic and pathogenic taxa, particularly members of the ESKAPEE group. Although
284 species-level identification was not possible within the scope of this study, *Klebsiella*,
285 *Enterobacter*, and *Acinetobacter* showed consistent enrichment in untreated communities across
286 both plumbing locations (all $P < 0.01$), with effect sizes ranging from 0.130 to 0.366 (Fig. 5, Table
287 1). *Sphingomonas*, *Comamonas*, *Agrobacterium*, and *Chryseobacterium* were also enriched, which
288 represent bacteria adapted to nutrient-rich environments typical of biofilms that are formed in
289 untreated plumbing systems.

290

291 **Discussion**

292 Our characterization of temporal dynamics, community structure, and taxonomic composition in
293 hospital sinks suggests that enhanced cleaning using hydrogen peroxide, peracetic acid, treatment
294 increases infection control through community-level disturbance and ecological replacement,
295 rather than broad bacterial suppression. Observable effects were restricted to plumbing
296 components (tail pieces and P-traps), demonstrating that Virasept imposes localized selection
297 pressures that restructure bacterial communities at the site of application and immediate adjacent
298 locations. This could be due to a limited contribution of bacteria from sinks to countertops relative
299 to inputs from air and room occupants^{32,33}. Cleaner application results in reduced temporal
300 predictability and directional drift that disrupts normal biofilm successional patterns, while
301 maintaining consistent compositional responses to environmental perturbations. Most
302 significantly, the treatment consistently favors soil- and water-associated bacteria (~85% of
303 enriched taxa) over healthcare-associated pathogens, creating stable alternative community states
304 dominated by nitrogen-fixing rhizosphere bacteria, spore-forming environmental taxa, and stress-
305 tolerant Actinobacteria. The strong correlation between tail piece and P-trap responses ($r = 0.611$,
306 $P < 0.001$), coupled with the suppression of ESKAPEE pathogens across both locations, indicates
307 that enhanced cleaning alters community dynamics potentially allowing for competitive exclusion
308 rather than stochastic antimicrobial effects. These findings challenge conventional approaches to
309 environmental disinfection by demonstrating that targeted environmental manipulation can alter
310 ecological dynamics in ways that provide pathogen control through the establishment of
311 environmentally beneficial bacteria.

312 Although overall community volatility was similar between treatments, temporal dynamics
313 diverged in ways that reveal a more nuanced treatment effect (Fig. 1). Treated tail piece
314 communities showed reduced week-to-week predictability (lag-1 ACF = -0.06 vs. 0.16 in
315 untreated samples), indicating that treatment suppresses biofilm-forming taxa in favor of more
316 transient species. Treated communities consistently clustered in a low-autocorrelation, low-drift
317 quadrant, reflecting what we term controlled instability — treatment prevents normal biofilm
318 successional patterns without generating stochastic fluctuations (Fig. 2). This distinguishes the
319 treatment effect from simple destabilization and instead suggests an alternative resilience dynamic
320 in which communities remain responsive to environmental perturbations but cannot establish the
321 predictable successional trajectories characteristic of untreated sinks. In P-traps, the response was
322 less strong. Treatment significantly reduced R^2 but did not alter the ACF, suggesting that there was
323 only partial community disruption (Fig. 2). This likely reflects physical and ecological features of
324 P-traps, which continually retain liquid and might receive elevated nutrient inputs depending on
325 sink use, supporting greater biofilm development. Dilution of the cleaner in the P-trap liquid could
326 be an additional factor, reducing its efficacy relative to the tail piece location. This has implications
327 for pathogen control and disease prevention within the hospital, since the tail piece can be rapidly
328 colonized by bacteria in the P-trap if enhanced cleaning is applied infrequently, or if regular use is
329 halted. Integration of volatility and stability analyses demonstrated that treatment effects operate
330 through controlled ecological disruption rather than community destabilization. The combination
331 of consistent weekly volatility responses (small effect sizes with statistical significance due to tight
332 distributions) and altered temporal stability patterns (disrupted autocorrelation and drift) indicate
333 that Virasept treatment maintains dynamic community responsiveness while preventing the
334 establishment of predictable biofilm successional patterns that are typical of untreated sinks.

335 These differences were further reflected in the bacterial community diversity and composition.
336 There were significant decreases in predicted richness within treated tail pieces and P-traps, with
337 no differences among countertops (Fig. 3A). This may be due to the removal of rare species or
338 selection for stress-tolerant taxa that are able to survive enhanced cleaning regimes. There was
339 also a divergence in community membership for both plumbing sites (Fig. 3B). Although many of
340 the highly abundant taxa were shared between all locations (Fig. 4), there was a consistent decrease
341 in clinically relevant taxa and targeted ecological filtering.

342 Differential abundance analysis identified twice the number of differentially abundant
343 genera in the P-traps (n=41) versus the tail pieces (n=22) (Table 1). This is counterintuitive given
344 that the foaming agent targets the tail piece directly, but likely reflects the persistence of active
345 disinfectant compounds in the P-trap after the foam dissipates and drips down — even in diluted
346 form, prolonged contact time may amplify cumulative effects on P-trap communities, potentially
347 damaging biofilms and planktonic cells. Across both sites, treatment consistently suppressed
348 clinically relevant taxa, including multiple genera with ESKAPEE pathogens exhibiting effect
349 sizes > 0.2 , indicating substantial suppression in treated environments (*Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella*,
350 and *Acinetobacter*) (Fig. 5). With this decrease, there was a corresponding increase in
351 environmental bacteria. *Bradyrhizobium* showed the largest treatment effect ($|\text{effect}| > 0.6$),
352 representing an approximate 4-7 \log_2 fold difference in abundance between treatments (Fig. 5).
353 Generally, enriched genera were broadly characteristic of soil and water environments, including
354 nitrogen-fixing (*Mesorhizobium*), biodegradation-associated (*Rhodococcus*), spore-forming
355 (*Bacillus*, *Paenibacillus*), and freshwater (*Pelomonas*) taxa (Table 1). These organisms are slow
356 growing, stress tolerant, and are adapted to oligotrophic conditions, suggesting that Virasept
357 treatment creates selective pressures that favor environmental bacteria over hospital-adapted
358 pathogens through oxidative stress and nutrient limitation. Whether this constitutes true
359 competitive exclusion or simply improved detection of previously masked taxa due to reduced
360 background community abundance remains unknown.

361 A parallel culture-based analysis of the same samples observed a significantly higher
362 number of EIPs in samples from the untreated sinks²⁰, including *Acinetobacter*, *Enterobacter*, and
363 *Klebsiella* species, with *P. aeruginosa* as the only isolate identified to the species level. Few EIPs
364 were detected in countertop samples, resulting in mostly non-significant differences in detection
365 between the control and treatment groups. This result mirrors the non-significant differences in the
366 countertop bacterial community that we observed in the sequencing results. Importantly, *P.*
367 *aeruginosa* and *Stenotrophomonas spp.* were significantly reduced, an outcome our sequencing-
368 based approach was unable to detect. Future work would benefit from absolute quantification via
369 spike-in extraction controls, and from higher-resolution tools such as metagenomics or digital PCR
370 to identify clinically relevant genomic features and pathogenic strains.

371 The taxonomic composition of differentially abundant genera supports the hypothesis that
372 effective environmental disinfection should aim for ecological replacement rather than sterile

373 elimination. The predominance of soil- and water-associated bacteria (~85% of treated-enriched
374 taxa) demonstrates that Virasept treatment creates environmental conditions that consistently favor
375 outdoor bacteria over hospital-adapted pathogens. The enrichment of functionally diverse
376 environmental taxa indicates successful establishment of a stable, pathogen-resistant bacterial
377 community with maintained ecosystem functioning. This ecological approach to infection control
378 leverages competitive displacement, whereby environmentally adapted bacteria outcompete
379 hospital-associated pathogens through adaptation to oxidative stress and nutrient limitation
380 imposed by treatment regimens.

381

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392

393 **Conflict of Interest**

394 The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

395

396 **Data Availability**

397 Raw sequence files and metadata are publicly available in the National Center for Biotechnology
398 Information (NCBI) Sequence Read Archive (SRA), under BioProject ID: PRJNA1433472.
399 Additionally, preprocessing and analysis scripts are available on GitHub at
400 https://github.com/hillms/hospital_sink_disinfection

401

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488 **Figure 1. Bacterial community volatility by treatment and location in hospital sinks.**489 Week-to-week compositional change using Aitchison distances on genus-level relative
490 abundances comparing treated (blue) and untreated (red) samples across three locations. (A)

491 Overall community volatility, in which each point represents the mean Aitchison distance

492 between consecutive weeks for a single room. Higher values indicate greater compositional

493 turnover between consecutive sampling timepoints. (B) Weekly volatility trajectories

494 showing temporal patterns of community change over the 35-week study period. Points

495 represent mean Aitchison distances between consecutive weeks across all rooms within each

496 treatment-location combination. Shaded regions indicate standard error.

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Figure 2. Bacterial community instability and temporal dynamics by treatment and location in hospital sinks. Analysis based on centered log-ratio (CLR) transformed genus-level relative abundances for treated (blue) and untreated (red) samples, with points representing individual rooms. Temporal autocorrelation computed from Euclidean distances

504 between each timepoint and the room-specific centroid. PERMANOVA performed on
505 Aitchison distances. Rooms with ≥ 4 timepoints for ACF analysis and ≥ 5 timepoints for
506 PERMANOVA were included. (A) Short-term predictability measured by lag-1 temporal
507 autocorrelation (ACF) of distance-from-centroid time series. Values near 1 indicate highly
508 predictable week-to-week patterns; values near 0 indicate erratic temporal fluctuations.
509 Dashed horizontal line indicates ACF = 0. Statistical significance tested with Wilcoxon rank-
510 sum tests. (B) Directional drift quantified by PERMANOVA R^2 values measuring the
511 proportion of community variance explained by sampling week within each room. Higher R^2
512 indicates stronger temporal drift patterns; lower R^2 indicates stable or randomly fluctuating
513 communities. Filled circles indicate significant week effects ($P < 0.05$) and open circles
514 indicate non-significant effects. Statistical significance tested with Wilcoxon rank-sum tests.
515 (C) Joint instability landscape plotting autocorrelation against directional drift for each room.
516 Background quadrants provide ecological interpretation: upper-left = stable communities;
517 upper-right = predictable directional drift; lower-left = erratic instability; lower-right =
518 directional but unpredictable change. Dotted reference lines indicate median values across
519 the dataset. 80% confidence ellipses indicate group clustering patterns; diamond markers
520 indicate group centroids.
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Figure 3. Alpha and beta diversity analysis of bacterial communities in hospital sink samples. (A) Alpha diversity metrics comparing treated (blue) and untreated (red) samples across three locations. (B) Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) of Aitchison distances between bacterial communities. Ellipses represent 95% confidence intervals around group centroids.

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Figure 4. Taxonomic composition of dominant bacterial genera in hospital sink communities. Percent relative abundances of the 15 most abundant bacterial genera across treatment groups and sampling locations.

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Figure 5. Differentially abundant taxa between treated and untreated samples for the P-trap and tail piece. Calculated with ALDEx2. Effect size > 0: enriched in untreated samples; Effect size < 0: enriched in treated samples. Enlarged dots represent genera with ESKAPEE pathogens. Dashed lines represent significance thresholds.

545 **Tables**

546

547 **Table 1. Differential abundance analysis of bacterial genera in hospital sink samples.**

548 ALDEx2 analysis comparing treated versus untreated communities at P-trap and tail piece
549 sampling locations. Analysis performed on genus-level relative abundances. Only genera with
550 $\geq 5\%$ prevalence within each location were included. Results sorted by effect size magnitude.
551 No differentially abundant taxa identified from countertop samples.

552 * indicates genera with ESKAPEE pathogens

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Tail Piece					
Genus	Effect	BH(wi)	BH(we)	diff.btw	Direction
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i>	-0.801	0	0	-7.268	TREATED
<i>Afipia</i>	-0.459	0	0	-4.226	TREATED
<i>Rhodococcus</i>	-0.141	0.0141	0.0091	-0.832	TREATED
<i>Qipengyuania</i>	-0.129	0.028	0.0082	-0.971	TREATED
<i>Sporosarcina</i>	-0.119	0.0244	0.0464	-0.82	TREATED
<i>Mesorhizobium</i>	-0.117	0.0477	0.0109	-0.732	TREATED
<i>Cutibacterium</i>	-0.114	0.0234	0.0009	-0.785	TREATED
<i>Pelomonas</i>	-0.104	0.0536	0.0028	-0.898	TREATED
<i>Methylobacterium</i>	0.059	0.1714	0.0241	0.434	UNTREATED
<i>Enterobacter</i> *	0.128	0.0177	0.0045	1.014	UNTREATED
<i>Klebsiella</i> *	0.13	0.0234	0.0116	0.984	UNTREATED
<i>Bosea</i>	0.143	0.0245	0.012	0.977	UNTREATED
<i>Microbacterium</i>	0.144	0.0342	0.0241	1.02	UNTREATED
<i>Novosphingobium</i>	0.153	0.004	0.0409	1.366	UNTREATED
<i>Comamonas</i>	0.156	0.0076	0.0002	1.352	UNTREATED
<i>Acinetobacter</i> *	0.162	0.0062	0.0155	1.585	UNTREATED
<i>Brevundimonas</i>	0.211	0.0009	0.005	1.755	UNTREATED
<i>Sphingomonas</i>	0.298	0	0	2.475	UNTREATED
<i>Sphingobium</i>	0.303	0	0	3.09	UNTREATED
<i>Agrobacterium</i>	0.319	0	0	2.259	UNTREATED
<i>Stenotrophomonas</i>	0.356	0	0	3.393	UNTREATED

<i>Chryseobacterium</i>	0.374	0	0	2.929	UNTREATED
P-Trap					
Genus	Effect	BH(wi)	BH(we)	diff.btw	Direction
<i>Bradyrhizobium</i>	-0.625	0	0	-4.413	TREATED
<i>Bacillus</i>	-0.16	0.0201	0.0159	-0.958	TREATED
<i>Mycobacterium</i>	-0.156	0.0208	0.0169	-1.537	TREATED
<i>Paenibacillus</i>	-0.155	0.0145	0.0069	-1.107	TREATED
<i>Aerococcus</i>	-0.154	0.0252	0.0147	-0.948	TREATED
<i>Afipia</i>	-0.151	0.0185	0.1325	-1.221	TREATED
<i>Rhodococcus</i>	-0.15	0.009	0.0097	-0.873	TREATED
<i>JABCPE02</i>	-0.147	0.0461	0.0869	-0.8	TREATED
<i>Micrococcus</i>	-0.14	0.0341	0.0444	-0.791	TREATED
<i>Paracoccus</i>	-0.132	0.0412	0.0551	-0.717	TREATED
<i>Sporosarcina</i>	-0.132	0.0276	0.0309	-0.826	TREATED
<i>Methylobacterium</i>	-0.131	0.0399	0.3538	-0.81	TREATED
<i>Dermacoccus</i>	-0.129	0.0524	0.046	-0.765	TREATED
<i>Porphyromonas</i>	-0.12	0.0437	0.0622	-0.723	TREATED
<i>Telluria</i>	-0.117	0.043	0.0476	-0.704	TREATED
<i>Vermiphilus</i>	-0.115	0.0467	0.0239	-0.783	TREATED
<i>Fusobacterium</i>	-0.109	0.0457	0.0723	-0.642	TREATED
<i>Phytobacter</i>	0.068	0.2187	0.0211	0.478	UNTREATED
<i>Azonexus</i>	0.112	0.0672	0.033	0.762	UNTREATED
<i>Pseudoxanthomonas_A</i>	0.123	0.0494	0.0263	0.812	UNTREATED
<i>Pedobacter</i>	0.161	0.0206	0.0138	1.151	UNTREATED
<i>Acidovorax</i>	0.169	0.005	0.0008	1.604	UNTREATED
<i>Caulobacter</i>	0.189	0.0057	0.005	1.324	UNTREATED
<i>Cupriavidus</i>	0.191	0.0002	0.0004	1.54	UNTREATED
<i>Xenophilus</i>	0.209	0.0028	0.0001	1.343	UNTREATED
<i>Microbacterium</i>	0.212	0.001	0.0003	1.436	UNTREATED
<i>Acinetobacter *</i>	0.212	0.0018	0.0066	1.851	UNTREATED
<i>Brevundimonas</i>	0.268	0.0001	0.0014	1.97	UNTREATED
<i>Sphingomonas</i>	0.281	0	0	2.067	UNTREATED

<i>Klebsiella</i> *	0.297	0	0	2.386	UNTREATED
<i>Stenotrophomonas</i>	0.304	0	0	2.771	UNTREATED
<i>Variovorax</i>	0.312	0	0	2.734	UNTREATED
<i>Novosphingobium</i>	0.315	0	0	2.839	UNTREATED
<i>Azospira</i>	0.327	0	0	2.423	UNTREATED
<i>Sphingobacterium</i>	0.351	0	0	2.299	UNTREATED
<i>Enterobacter</i> *	0.366	0	0	3.078	UNTREATED
<i>Comamonas</i>	0.382	0	0	3.056	UNTREATED
<i>Agrobacterium</i>	0.384	0	0	2.67	UNTREATED
<i>Bosea</i>	0.418	0	0	3.048	UNTREATED
<i>Chryseobacterium</i>	0.446	0	0	3.535	UNTREATED
<i>Sphingobium</i>	0.47	0	0	4.276	UNTREATED
Tail Piece					
Genus	Effect	BH(wi)	BH(we)	diff.bt w	Direction
Bradyrhizobium	-0.801	0	0	-7.268	TREATED
Afipia	-0.459	0	0	-4.226	TREATED
Rhodococcus	-0.141	0.0141	0.0091	-0.832	TREATED
Qipengyuania	-0.129	0.028	0.0082	-0.971	TREATED
Sporosarcina	-0.119	0.0244	0.0464	-0.82	TREATED
Mesorhizobium	-0.117	0.0477	0.0109	-0.732	TREATED

Cutibacterium	- 0.11 4	0.023 4	0.000 9	-0.785	TREATE D
Pelomonas	- 0.10 4	0.053 6	0.002 8	-0.898	TREATE D
Methylobacterium	0.05 9	0.171 4	0.024 1	0.434	UNTREA TED
Enterobacter *	0.12 8	0.017 7	0.004 5	1.014	UNTREA TED
Klebsiella *	0.13	0.023 4	0.011 6	0.984	UNTREA TED
Bosea	0.14 3	0.024 5	0.012	0.977	UNTREA TED
Microbacterium	0.14 4	0.034 2	0.024 1	1.02	UNTREA TED
Novosphingobium	0.15 3	0.004	0.040 9	1.366	UNTREA TED
Comamonas	0.15 6	0.007 6	0.000 2	1.352	UNTREA TED
Acinetobacter *	0.16 2	0.006 2	0.015 5	1.585	UNTREA TED
Brevundimonas	0.21 1	0.000 9	0.005	1.755	UNTREA TED
Sphingomonas	0.29 8	0	0	2.475	UNTREA TED
Sphingobium	0.30 3	0	0	3.09	UNTREA TED
Agrobacterium	0.31 9	0	0	2.259	UNTREA TED
Stenotrophomonas	0.35 6	0	0	3.393	UNTREA TED
Chryseobacterium	0.37 4	0	0	2.929	UNTREA TED

P-Trap					
Genus	Effect	BH(wi)	BH(we)	diff.btw	Direction
Bradyrhizobium	- 0.625	0	0	-4.413	TREATED
Bacillus	- 0.16	0.0201	0.0159	-0.958	TREATED
Mycobacterium	- 0.156	0.0208	0.0169	-1.537	TREATED
Paenibacillus	- 0.155	0.0145	0.0069	-1.107	TREATED
Aerococcus	- 0.154	0.0252	0.0147	-0.948	TREATED
Afipia	- 0.151	0.0185	0.1325	-1.221	TREATED
Rhodococcus	- 0.15	0.009	0.0097	-0.873	TREATED
JABCPE02	- 0.147	0.0461	0.0869	-0.8	TREATED
Micrococcus	- 0.14	0.0341	0.0444	-0.791	TREATED
Paracoccus	- 0.132	0.0412	0.0551	-0.717	TREATED
Sporosarcina	- 0.132	0.0276	0.0309	-0.826	TREATED

Methylobacterium	- 0.13 1	0.039 9	0.353 8	-0.81	TREATE D
Dermacoccus	- 0.12 9	0.052 4	0.046	-0.765	TREATE D
Porphyromonas	- 0.12	0.043 7	0.062 2	-0.723	TREATE D
Telluria	- 0.11 7	0.043	0.047 6	-0.704	TREATE D
Vermiphilus	- 0.11 5	0.046 7	0.023 9	-0.783	TREATE D
Fusobacterium	- 0.10 9	0.045 7	0.072 3	-0.642	TREATE D
Phytobacter	0.06 8	0.218 7	0.021 1	0.478	UNTREA TED
Azonexus	0.11 2	0.067 2	0.033	0.762	UNTREA TED
Pseudoxanthomona s_A	0.12 3	0.049 4	0.026 3	0.812	UNTREA TED
Pedobacter	0.16 1	0.020 6	0.013 8	1.151	UNTREA TED
Acidovorax	0.16 9	0.005	0.000 8	1.604	UNTREA TED
Caulobacter	0.18 9	0.005 7	0.005	1.324	UNTREA TED
Cupriavidus	0.19 1	0.000 2	0.000 4	1.54	UNTREA TED
Xenophilus	0.20 9	0.002 8	0.000 1	1.343	UNTREA TED
Microbacterium	0.21 2	0.001	0.000 3	1.436	UNTREA TED

Acinetobacter *	0.21 2	0.001 8	0.006 6	1.851	UNTREA TED
Brevundimonas	0.26 8	0.000 1	0.001 4	1.97	UNTREA TED
Sphingomonas	0.28 1	0	0	2.067	UNTREA TED
Klebsiella *	0.29 7	0	0	2.386	UNTREA TED
Stenotrophomonas	0.30 4	0	0	2.771	UNTREA TED
Variovorax	0.31 2	0	0	2.734	UNTREA TED
Novosphingobium	0.31 5	0	0	2.839	UNTREA TED
Azospira	0.32 7	0	0	2.423	UNTREA TED
Sphingobacterium	0.35 1	0	0	2.299	UNTREA TED
Enterobacter *	0.36 6	0	0	3.078	UNTREA TED
Comamonas	0.38 2	0	0	3.056	UNTREA TED
Agrobacterium	0.38 4	0	0	2.67	UNTREA TED
Bosea	0.41 8	0	0	3.048	UNTREA TED
Chryseobacterium	0.44 6	0	0	3.535	UNTREA TED
Sphingobium	0.47	0	0	4.276	UNTREA TED

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Supplementary Material

556 **Table S1. Significance results for per-week volatility analysis.** P-values are calculated
 557 based on PERMANOVA with week as the sole predictor of Aitchison distance. * = $p < 0.05$
 558 (significant), ** = $p < 0.01$ (highly significant), *** = $p < 0.001$ (very highly significant), —
 559 = insufficient data
 560

Week	Tail Piece	P-Trap	Countertop
1	0.022*	0.031*	0.189
2	0.002**	0.003**	0.134
3	-	0.08	0.104
4	0.052	0.864	-
5	0.001**	-	0.595
6	0.001**	0.908	0.56
7	0.247	-	0.182
8	0.2	-	0.836
9	0.2	0.019*	0.844
10	0.078	0.091	0.896
11	0.155	0.186	0.93
12	0.001**	0.12	0.672
13	0.085	0.002**	0.845
14	0.005**	0.004**	0.011*
15	0.12	0.07	0.109
16	0.047*	0.424	0.46
17	0.001**	0.772	-
18	0.663	0.007**	0.198
20	0.061	0.001**	0.773
21	0.001**	0.001**	0.296
22	0.003**	0.007**	0.786
24	0.001**	0.001**	0.737
26	0.001**	0.004**	0.216
27	0.155	0.135	0.465
28	0.001**	0.001**	0.404
29	0.001**	0.3	0.41

30	-	0.028*	0.142
31	0.018*	-	0.946
32	0.005**	0.008**	0.945
33	0.001**	-	0.562
34	0.002**	-	0.506
35	0.001**	-	0.327